

**Exploring the Potential of Computer-Aided Architectural Design (CAAD)
Applications in Architectural Technology Education at Kaduna Polytechnic
Nigeria**

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Abstract

The primary goal of architectural technology education is to equip individuals with functional, technical, vocational, and entrepreneurial skills that contribute to personal and national development. However, the evolving demands and trends in architecture necessitate architects to possess a broader skill set that goes beyond traditional requirements of conceptualization, analysis, and design production. To address these changing requirements, it is crucial to adopt a training approach that recognizes the importance of new tools and methods offered by technological advancements. One area where technological integration is particularly relevant is Computer-Aided Architectural Design (CAAD). CAAD refers to specialized software that assists in visualizing designs as 3D computer models, facilitating accurate conceptualization, simulation, and design development. This paper explores the potential of integrating CAAD into the training curriculum, focusing on its ability to meet architects' problem-solving needs within an instructional framework. Specifically, the paper reviews courses such as Architectural Design Studio, Graphics, Delineation, and Site Planning, which directly benefit from CAAD-related content. These courses in terms of their compatibility with CAAD. The paper also examines the current training expectations based on the curriculum and explores how CAAD can address these expectations. Additionally, it discusses the challenges associated with acquiring real-world skills in CAAD for architectural technologists. The finding of the study revealed that 94 (62.7%) respondents agreed that the CAAD knowledge acquired in school will assist them in future. Furthermore, the paper identifies opportunities for curriculum improvement and proposes recommendations for integrating specific CAAD-related content into the curriculum guidelines. It also

highlights areas where intervention and revisions of the current study content are necessary to enhance both staff and students' proficiency in CAAD applications, aligning with the National Education Policy's objectives.

Keywords: Application, Architecture, CAAD, Education, Technology.

1. INTRODUCTION

Computer-Aided Design (CAD) simply refers to the process whereby computers and specialist software are used to produce virtual three-dimensional models and two-dimensional drawings of products. (Olukoya & Oluwaseun, 2015). There are several types of CAD software which include Revit, ArchiCAD, Sketchup, AutoCAD, VectorWorks, and 3DMAX among others; that have been developed for use in a range of applications and industries.

Architectural education has evolved to integrate innovative technological tools in alignment with rapidly shifting global market behaviours. The use of innovative technological tools in studio environments must encourage students to work more collaboratively yet foster autonomy. (Sireesha, 2018).

The mission of the Polytechnic Education in Nigeria is teaching, technical and vocational training for the production of quality graduates, innovative information and improvement in technology and the educational objectives are conceived in the effort by individual institutions to produce proficient higher and lower technicians that will occupy the middle-level manpower cadre (Olukoya & Oluwaseun, 2015)

Uwakonye et al.,(2015) say that Architectural technology programmes offered in Nigerian polytechnics are accredited by the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE), leading to the award of National Diploma (ND) and Higher National Diploma (HND) certificates in Architectural technology. Opoola, (2020) the mission of the programme is the provision of functional, technical, vocational and entrepreneurial education and training which targets individual and national development. The main objective of the programme is to provide contemporary and sustainable manpower nurtured by ICT-driven human resources development which will remain responsive to the dynamism of the practice environment in Nigeria.(Opoola, 2020)

Since the effects of technology on architectural education remain profound, students and instructors must work stridently towards closing theoretical and practical

knowledge gaps to produce more sustainable outcomes. By drawing from critical theory, instructors in architectural education programs focus seminar discussions on how various dimensions of society drive major shifts in design principles (Alias et al., 2014; Opoola, 2020). However, researchers have identified a significant divide between architectural theory and practice (Kocaturk & Kiviniemi, 2013). When instructors of architectural programs draw primarily from critical theory to critique the role of technology and deliver seminar materials covering design principles, discussions may turn into political debates about which cultural variables will influence practice. (Sireesha, 2018). Researchers inspired by educational theory have discussed the impacts of technology on academic program outcomes suggesting that an emphasis on visual training produces sound aesthetic judgments. Specifically, Jones (2016) noted how the 80-year tradition of education theory needs instructors capable of challenging dominant theoretical paradigms. Technological innovation allows university instructors and faculty to challenge assumptions about what types of coursework will produce students who achieve success after completing a graduate-level program. (Jones, 2016).

Rana & Ihsan, (2017) states that the internet, advanced illustration tools and software are obvious examples of this digital revolution that has affected the very process of teaching architectural design. Thus, the development of such digital tools over a relatively short time and their continuous advancement and refinement had and continues to have, an inevitable major impact on many key pedagogical aspects of architectural education and curricula design. Although Computer-Aided Architectural Design (CAAD), was introduced into most, if not all, the architectural design departments at Kaduna Polytechnic, students are not allowed to use it unless they finish their first two years of the architectural education program as they must, due to their curriculum, to learn the basic hand sketching and other hand communication skills in order to apply it in their designs. (Uwakonye et al., 2015). Though this transition is not clearly addressed, thus students are left unable to implement this blend of methods when needed. Uwakonye et al., (2015) Moreover, some students are not able to employ Computer-Aided Architectural Design (CAAD) tools in designing different processes, for example, they cannot use Computer-Aided Architectural Design (CAAD) to better understand their projects' different components and systems,

for example the structure, electro-mechanical, heating, ventilation, and air conditioning, etc. Computer-Aided Architectural Design (CAAD) tools and software are not taught as design or analysing tools or programs, thus students are not able to analyse the environmental aspects of the site. As a consequence, students are not able to implement their learned skills in Computer-Aided Architectural Design(CAAD) to their design projects in practical manner to deliver integrated designs unless and until they find themselves in the working environment. (Rana & Ihsan, 2017).

This paper grows out of a desire to observe if what is being taught and how it is being taught is sufficient to prepare the architectural technology students with the necessary cognitive and practical abilities for the present work demands of architectural practice in Nigeria. This is particularly relevant to the country at a period when graduate unemployment rate is at 25%. The United Nations demographic experts have estimated that by 2050 over 70% of the population in Nigeria would reside in the urban centres (Marcel-Okafor, 2017). Nigeria, with a population of over 150 million people, 70% of who are classified as being poor and, an estimated annual growth rate of 3.2%, remains the fastest urbanising and most populous country in Sub-Saharan Africa (Marcel-Okafor, 2017).

Architectural technology programmes suffer the same prejudice meted out on the entire polytechnic education in Nigeria which is worrisome; this is because of the general preference in Nigeria to paper certification which the university education favourably offers against the technical certification which the polytechnic education offers. This socio-political bigotry against technical education has devalued the entire polytechnic education despite the practice-based learning style inherent in it, which is germane to unleashing the technological potentials and breakthroughs needed for national development in the country. (Marcel-Okafor, 2017).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Curriculum

The curriculum of architectural technology programmes like other academic curricula of professions is the body of knowledge that houses all the experiences, skills, creativity and activities going on in the school environment in order to achieve educational goals (Marcel-Okafor, 2017) The current curriculum content in the Nigerian schools of architecture is structured to have tutorial courses revolve around studio design which is the core course that carries both the highest contact hours and credit loads (Agbo, Ogbonna , & Okwoli, 2017)

This is also the scenario in the architectural technology departments in polytechnics, where the design studio is both the teaching and learning environment as well as the core course of study of architecture students. Olutuah, Taiwo, & Ijatuyi (2016) emphasises that this implies that it is germane to the study of architectural technology and as such dependent on the pedagogy and curriculum of the school, (Olutuah, Taiwo, & Ijatuyi, 2016).

(Olutuah, 2006) asserts that since the central issue in architecture is the quality of the human habitat, the goal of architectural education is generally directed towards the attainment of a humane and responsive environment. The extent to which this goal is successfully attained depends on the curriculum content as approved by the regulatory body and various polytechnics, and methods of teaching the courses adopted by the lecturers and technologists. (Marcel-Okafor, 2017) succinctly posits that the structure of the architectural curriculum should aim at giving expressions to and utilizing the factors of socioeconomic and technological transformations in Nigeria.

The curriculum of the ND and HND Architectural Technology programmes consists of four components.

1. General Studies: These include courses in art and humanities, mathematics and sciences, social and entrepreneurship studies. This component accounts for a maximum of 10% of the total contact hours for the programme.
2. Foundation Courses: These include courses in pure sciences, economics, statistics and account for 10- 15% of the total contact hours for the programme.

3. Professional Courses: These include theoretical and practical courses in the field of study and provide the student with cognitive and practical skills needed to practice. Consequently, they account for 70-80% of the contact hours for the programme.

4. SIWES for ND programme: the following criteria are used for assessment of this component; i) punctuality ii) attendance iii) general attitude to work iv) technical competence v) respect for authority vi) interest in the field. Olutuah, Taiwo, & Ijatuyi, (2016). The

professional courses which make up the core courses are grouped into six main areas of study or instruction modules as follows.

1. Architectural design courses
2. Architectural graphics courses
3. Architectural professional administration courses
4. Building construction courses
5. Computer courses
6. Entrepreneurial/ Environmental Courses

2.2 Teaching methods

Good teaching is tuition that results in useful acquisition of knowledge. Good quality teaching requires a good combination of subject knowledge, teaching methodology, psychology of learning and of learners as well as astute resourceful attitudinal orientation characteristic of the teacher. The current teaching method in architectural technology programmes in Nigeria was believed to have developed in Europe and was rooted in two schools: the Ecole des Beaux Arts and the Bauhaus (Gudey, 2015).

The former was based on studio-oriented design education while the latter ushered in the lecture format to studios and played a complimentary role as the information acquired from the lecture series were intended to intellectually equip the trainees in their studio exercises (Jones, 2016). Pedagogy-based training enables teachers to appreciate the role of learning theory in the plan and purpose of class activities and in the selection and use of instructional technologies (Agbo, Ogbonna, & Okwoli, 2017). The learning theories which represent hypothetical structures necessary for the assimilation and effective utilisation of acquired knowledge are crucial to both the

application of the teaching methods and the implementation of the curriculum in architectural technology.

This implies that the strategies used to impart knowledge and the curriculum must reflect in the output or practice performance of the architectural technologist. The polytechnics have also adopted the lecturing style of teaching which basically involves passing information orally and remains the exclusive of those in the lecturing cadre while the practical aspects of illustrations and student physical participation are handled by the technologists.

The methods of teaching commonly used are lecture methods, discussion methods, and the demonstration methods. The lecture formats commonly used are;

1. The participatory/inquiry method
2. The problem-solving method
3. The creative/construction method
4. The case study method

Effects of Computer-Aided Designs (CAD) on Architecture

“The machine is the architect’s tool -whether he likes it or not. Unless he masters it, the machine has mastered him” Arc. Frank Lloyd Wright. No matter how much CAD has helped in producing designs, the designer will encounter limitations in the use of CAD. As he or she tackles these limitations, more knowledge of computer programming is required. Computer-Aided Architectural Design (CAAD) has had a radical impact upon the teaching, learning and practice of design (Gudey, 2015).

One can create conceptual detailed designs of 2-D and 3-D drawings, environmental impact reports, manipulate the shape of images and tackle more complex design problems in faster time with the aid of CAAD. CAAD technology existence in architecture has two primary objectives which are to be applied in human cognitive design process through the computing smart technology and to become an idea representative media in architectural design process (Gudey, 2015). Therefore, the effects of the use of Computer-Aided Architectural Design (CAAD) will be discussed under the following aegis.

Figure 1: 2D floor plan using CAAD using Revit software version 2016

Source: Researchers field work,2020

Figure 2: 3D CAAD using Revit software version 2016

Source: Researchers field work,2020

Figure 3 Approach view using CAAD using Revit software version 2016

Source: Researchers field work, 2020

2.3 The State of CAAD Education in Architecture Schools in Nigeria

CAAD has been used in Nigeria since the mid-1990s. Several Architectural firms and contracting companies were interested in the potential of digital technologies as drafting and modeling tools. As an educational tool, CAAD software was installed as an introductory course for undergraduate architectural programs in 1994, but there were only a few faculty members who could teach it then. Several years later, CAAD courses became obligatory (i.e., CAAD I, CAAD II) over two semesters, typically for second-year students, (Abu Ghanima, 2006). Moreover, most schools of architecture in Nigeria attempted to update their curricula through software and digital technologies to bridge the gaps between design theory and practice. Since 2014, however, some schools have begun to re-think the use of digital software as an analytical, generative and constructive tool. Consequently, software such as “Revit” and “Introduction to BIM” were installed in their curricula (Al-Matarneh & Fethi, 2017).

(Adegbesan, 2011; Uwakonye et al., 2015) asserted that generally, schools of architecture in Nigeria combine the physical method with the digital method to ensure that students enjoy the benefits of both methods. Thus, most, if not all, schools of

architecture prohibit the use of CAAD tools in design for students in their first two years. Design teaching for first- and second-year studios emphasize on the importance of developing manual graphic communication skills, sketching, and the experience of making physical models. However, the current curriculum of architectural design education in most schools suffers from a lack of synchronization and integration between computer courses and design projects. Furthermore,(Adegbesan, 2011) stated that the prevalent tendency at present is to treat each course as a separate entity with its own distinct particularity, which prevents the necessary coordination between theoretical and design courses and applied computer courses. Moreover, although the structure of the curricula remains relatively flexible to manage new digital technologies, integrating these technologies with design courses is highly advisable and will ensure a more holistic and creative environment and not to use this software only as drafting tools. Example of CADD design.

Figure 4 Plan view using CAAD using Revit software version 2016

Source: Researchers field work,2020

3. METHODS

Purposive sampling technique was used. Sample were drawn from selection government owned polytechnics that offer Architectural Technology programme in Nigeria. Primary data were obtained using structured interviews administered to the staff of the selected polytechnics, and students. Sampled surveyed were obtained from the polytechnic to ascertain the use of CAAD as one of the methods of teaching in the schools. The interviews focused on teaching methods used and the assessment of the performance of the graduates in practice on a five-point scale as well as challenges encountered. Secondary data used were obtained from academic curricula for architectural technology programmes of the selected polytechnics, refereed journals, some reports available from reliable internet sources and books.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the distribution of sampled by the target group. The polytechnics are Kaduna Polytechnic, Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic Zaria, Kaduna State and kano state polytechnic.

Table 1 showing the distribution of sampled respondents by the three (3) polytechnic

S/ N	TYPE OF INSTITUTION	INSTITUTION NAME	ACADEMIC STAFF	STUDENTS	TOTAL
1	FEDERAL	KADUNA POLYTECHNIC, KADUNA	25	30	55
2	STATE	NUHU BAMBALLI POLYTECHNIC, ZARIA	25	30	55
3	STATE	KANO STATE POLYTECHNIC, KANO	20	30	50

Source: Researchers field work, 2020

The data collected were analyzed using of frequencies, percentages and Chi square to test the significance of CAAD as a tool in teaching methods and courses taught and the effective Use of CAAD. The intention of this study was to analyze courses presented in the curricula with regard to utilize CAAD potentials in the requirements

and expectations of the students to ascertain their relevance to present day architectural practice. To effectively measure the practice performance of the students. This study examined the benchmark for ascertaining work expectations as stipulated in the NBTE regulated curriculum for architectural technology programme and the actual work requirements and achievements in the professional practice.

The researcher used questionnaire as an instrument for collecting data considering the nature and predisposition of the respondents. The instrument used was designed to ensure that relevant data were collected. A questionnaire consists of a set of questions presented to a respondent for answers. The respondents read the questions, interpret what is expected and then write down the answers themselves. Because there are many ways of asking questions, the questionnaire is very flexible. Questionnaire should be developed and tested carefully before being used on a large scale.

The population for this study is Kaduna polytechnic ,Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic, Zaria and Kano state polytechnic, Kano. The choice of this institution was made because both federal and state institutions have common characteristics of managing the system. The target group for the study will be made up of the Academic Staff and Students of the polytechnic. With regards to the category of the entire population of the study, this is made of the three(3) Polytechnic. The academic staff, and students of the School of Architecture form the sample of the study. The intention of this study was to analyse courses presented in the curricula with regard to utilising CAAD potentials in the requirements and expectations of the students to ascertain their relevance to present-day architectural practice. To effectively measure the practice performance of the students.

The table below shows the effectiveness of courses learnt and the perceived impact on CAAD in places of work. The p-value (0.00) which is less than the alpha (0.05) or 95% in the table above shows that there is a significant association between the final year courses taught and the impact of CAAD on the student's performance in the future. This implies that the teaching methods were effective.

Table 2. Showing the effectiveness of courses learnt and perceived impact on CAAD in places of work

		Do you agree that the CAAD knowledge acquired in school will assist you in future?	
		Agree	Strongly agree
The final year courses learnt in school that will help you in professional practice	Architectural delineation	95 (97.72)	56 (52.28)
	Construction drawing	94 (97.72)	56 (52.28)
	Application of computer in Architecture	94 (97.72)	56 (52.28)
	Measurement of building works	5 (6.51)	5 (3.49)
	Environmental science	25 (16.29)	0 (0.00)
	Interior design	5 (9.12)	9 (4.88)
	Introduction to modern Architecture	40 (31.92)	9 (4.88)

Researchers field work, 2020

The study revealed that 94 (62.7%) respondents agreed that the CAAD knowledge acquired in school will assist them in future, while 56 (37.3%) strongly agreed. There were no responses for 'disagree', 'strongly disagree', and 'No Idea'. Lecturing is the predominant teaching method, the lecturers are freely disposed to any of the lecture format; creative/constructive method, problem solving method. The results showed that 18 (43.9%) of the staff respondents from the schools are of the opinion that course content and class size determine their choice of teaching method adopted, while 15 (36.6%) were of the opinion that course content only determines the choice and 8 (19.5%) are influenced by class size alone. See Table 3.

Table 3. Showing factors that influence choice of teaching methods.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative %
Course Content	15	36.6	36.6	36.6
Class size	8	19.5	19.5	56.1
Course content and class size	18	43.9	43.9	100.0
Total	41	100.0	100.0	

Researchers field work,2020

Table 4. Showing the responses on the performance of the students

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Above average	15	36.6	36.6	36.6
Average	26	63.4	63.4	100.0
Total	41	100.0	100.0	

Researchers field work,2020

The study revealed that 26 (63%) of the respondents ranked the performance of their students as average, while 15 (36.6%) said their students performed above average. There were no responses for below-average and poor performance in using CAAD. Showed on table 4 Above.

Table 5 showing the attitudes toward the importance of CAAD compared with traditional methods

Researchers field work, 2020

Figure 5 showing that the majority of respondents with about (85%) described their attitudes positively toward the importance of CAAD compared with traditional methods. However, 5% of the respondents were indifferent, they are not sure while 10% of the respondents had negative attitudes regarding the use of CAAD they prefer the use of traditional methods.

Researchers fieldwork, 2020

Table 6 showing the attitudes toward Using CAAD among architecture students.

Researchers field work, 2020

Table 6: showing the superiority of using CAAD over the traditional method of sketching, 80% of the students preferred to use CAAD media over traditional methods, whereas traditional-method users accounted for only 5% of the total respondents above. A great interest in CAAD was noted among all respondents. There seems to be a strong trend for architectural students to convert from traditional methods to CAAD. The dramatic increase of CAAD users suggests that there should be a serious reconsideration of the current curriculum to adapt to the new CAAD trends.

Finally, this paper assessed the impact of CAAD tools on the design process and on the quality of the architectural end product at three schools of architecture at Kaduna Polytechnic, Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic Zaria and Kano state polytechnic. The findings revealed that all three schools have almost the same architectural design educational approach that mixes traditional design methods with digital methods. Analyses revealed that the majority of students were found to have a strong tendency to use CAAD software programmes for their various advantages, such as accuracy, neatness, speed and lower cost, etc. Presently, the mode of teaching CAAD in most, if not all, of the architectural departments in the polytechnic does not encourage the use of CAAD in the early phase of the design, just like in the conceptual stage. The

study shows that CAAD tools have not been integrated into the creation processes of the conceptual architectural design and the influence of the CAAD tools in the conceptual design phase is still very minor. Moreover, all interviewees agreed that the creation procedure has not been influenced by the adoption of digital tools. At the same time, findings from the analysed design projects showed that the presented projects are seductive graphic more than realistic architecture. CAAD is still being considered, perceived and utilized as drafting, modelling, and rendering tool rather than as a problem-solving strategy. Simultaneously, this restricts the potential use of CAAD to develop already created designs, but not to use it as a tool to generate new design. Very few analysed projects showed the use of CAAD as medium to create an innovative form in the geometrical formation and conceptual phase. This assures (Botchway, Amos-Abanyie, & Afram, 2015) findings, when he assessed the impact of CAAD Design Tools on Architectural Design Education, as he found out that CAAD is taught in isolation of other design courses in the department. The transformation of students' design trends from traditional methods to CAAD is still not clearly defined. And this affects students' ability to transfer their skills that are learned through traditional methods to the more complicated CAAD method. All the three departments of architectural technology are in government owned polytechnics and have been fully accredited at both the National Diploma (ND) and Higher National Diploma (HND) levels by the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) (see Table 7).

Table 7: Showing background information of selected institutions

Name of Institution	Kaduna Polytechnic Kaduna State	Nuhu Bamalli State Polytechnic Zaria	Kano State Polytechnic
Year of establishment	1956	1989	1976
Ownership	Federal	State	State
Status	government	government	government
Programmes offered	ND/HND	ND/HND	ND/HND
Accreditation Status	Fully accredited	Fully accredited	Fully accredited

Source: NBTE, 2017

Table 8: Showing list of courses offered at HND1 Programme

Kaduna Polytechnic, Kaduna State	Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic, Zaria	Kano State Polytechnic Kano State
1989 reviewed version of NBTE accredited curriculum and course specification	1989 version of NBTE accredited curriculum and course specification	1989 version of NBTE accredited curriculum and course specification
ARC311 Architectural Design and Report	ARC311 Architectural Design and Report	ARC311 Architectural Design and Report
ARC312 Architectural Delineation	ARC312 Architectural Delineation	ARC312 Architectural Delineation
ARC313 Construction Methods	ARC313 Construction Methods	ARC313 Construction Methods
ARC314 Architectural Detailing	ARC314 Architectural Detailing	ARC314 Architectural Detailing
ARC 315 Technical Report Writing	ARC 315 Technical Report Writing	ARC 315 Technical Report Writing
ARC316 Building Climatology	ARC316 Building Climatology	ARC316 Building Climatology
ARC 317 Site Planning and Landscape Design	ARC 317 Site Planning and Landscape Design	ARC 317 Site Planning and Landscape Design
ARC 318 Estimating and Tendering	ARC 318 Estimating and Tendering	ARC 318 Estimating and Tendering
Advanced Mathematics for Architecture	Advanced Mathematics for Architecture	Advanced Mathematics for Architecture
Outline History of Africa	Outline History of Africa	Outline History of Africa
Architectural Appreciation/Theory	N/A	N/A

Source: NBTE, 2017

Table 9: Showing courses offered at HND11 programme

Kaduna Polytechnic,kad una state	North Bamalli Polytech nic Zaria	Kano State Polytechnic,Kan o State
ARC411 Architectural Design and Report III	ARC411 Architectural Design and Report	ARC411 Architectural Design and Report
ARC412 Architectural Delineation III	ARC412 Architectural Delineation III	ARC412 Architectural Delineation III
ARC413 Construction Drawings I	ARC413 Construction Drawings I	ARC413 Construction Drawings I
ARC414 Electrical	ARC414 Electrical	ARC414 Electrical

Building Services ARC415 Specification Writing	Building Services ARC415 Specification Writing	Building Services ARC415 Specification Writing
ARC416 Principles and Practice of Building Maintenance	ARC416 Principles and Practice of Building Maintenance	ARC416 Principles and Practice of Building Maintenance
ARC 417 Application of Computer in Architecture II	ARC 417 Application of Computer in Architecture II	ARC 417 Application of Computer in Architecture II
ARC 418 Environmental Science	N/A	N/A
Measurement of Building Works II Introduction Psychology	Measurement of Building Works II Introduction Psychology	Measurement of Building Works II Introduction Psychology
Entrepreneurship Development	Entrepreneurship Development	Entrepreneurship Development

Researchers field work,2020

Table 9: Showing courses offered and objectives from NBTE curriculum.

Objectives from NBTE curriculum	Courses that target the criterion	Software Recommendation	Remarks
Ability to make sketches based on the brief.	Architectural Delineation	Sketchup 2016 version, Archicad,2015	very good
Ability to incorporate superior comments	Architectural Design	AutoCad 2016 version,Revit	excellent
Ability to produce drawings using software.	Construction Drawings Architectural Delineation and Application of Computer In Architecture II	AutoCad 2016 version	excellent
Ability to produce designs that satisfy brief	Architectural Design	AutoCad 2016 version,Revit	good
Ability to produce standard designs.	Architectural Design and Professional Administration	AutoCad 2016 version	good
Ability to produce cost effective designs	Architectural Design and Estimating and Tendering	AutoCad 2016 version	good
Complete designs within the target time frame.	Architectural Design and Professional Admin.	AutoCad 2016 version	very good
Ability to assist in supervision of construction works.	Construction Methods, Principles and Practice of Building Maintenance	AutoCad 2016 version	Fairly good
Ability to make progress reports.	Technical Report Writing	AutoCad 2016 version	poor

Researchers field work, 2020

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are proposed:

1. Adequate provisions of infrastructural facilities to effectively implement the use of CADD design as a teaching and learning tool which will encourage assimilation of design and technological advances of the 21st century.
2. Collaboration of polytechnics to review and implementation of the curriculum so as to have a common curriculum especially for core courses by utilizing CADD design as a modern tool in teaching and learning.
3. There needs to for a paradigm shift in the value system for polytechnic education in the country, which encourages staff to utilised the use of CADD by staff development training as a tool of teaching and to place technical education in its right place this will encourage more individuals to opt for polytechnic education and receive job satisfaction through enhanced productivity.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper has documented the current curriculum contents of some polytechnics in Nigeria as well as the job expectations of the architectural technologists. Based on the literature it is critical that that the utilization of Computer-Aided Architectural Design (CAAD) training to both staff and students as a modern way of teaching and learning in the polytechnics with modern advances in design and technology in order to attain far-reaching results. The study has shown that improving the quality and methods of teaching as well as periodic review of the curriculum content are geared towards quality of graduates and their professional performance. The results will include effective amelioration of the computer-Aided Architectural Design (CAAD) as a tool that assists the drafting procedure. It has no place in the thinking process and has very little influence on the initial stages of design. It is only a physical tangible tool which transforms the abstraction of the user into reality on the paperless board just like the old traditional method design. Furthermore, the architectural school's instructors should encourage the students to imbibe the practices of Computer-Aided Architectural Design CADD as the basics of the design process. This study posits that the successful fusion of traditional design construction and technological use of Computer-Aided Architectural Design (CAAD) will produce excellent products as finished designs. Thus, in the Architectural trainings as well as practices, there should

be a balance in the use of traditional methods as well as the computer-Aided Architectural Design (CAAD) as a complete architect that has mastered various techniques to proffer design solutions.

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She is currently a Lecturer at Kaduna Polytechnic, has been teaching Architecture related courses and holds other responsibilities within the Department amongst others. Master's degree (MSc Arch) holder from Architecture Department, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.

She holds membership with the Association of Architectural Educators in Nigeria (AARCHES), Nigerian Institute of Architects (NIA), Teachers Registration Council (TRCN), Provisional Membership with the Architects Registration Council of Nigeria (ARCON), and Nigerian Environmental Society (NES).

2

Fatima Baba Ciroma

She is currently a lecturer, Principal Lecturer (PL) at Kaduna Polytechnic in Nigeria. She holds a master's degree in architecture and a B. Tech in Architecture from Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi. Her lecturing career began in 2010 at the Department of Architecture at Kaduna Polytechnic, where she currently teaches Architecture related courses and holds other responsibilities within the Department. Fatima is currently pursuing a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Architecture at Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. Fatima has actively participated in various International and National Conferences and Workshops. She is a member of several professional organizations, including the Nigerian Institute of Architects (ANIA), provisional membership with the Architects Registration Council of Nigeria (ARCON), Association of Architectural Educators of Nigeria (AARCHES), Women in Technical Education and Development (WITED), Nigerian Environmental Society (NES), Green Building Council of Nigeria (GBCN), and Teachers Registration Council (TRCN), among others. In addition to her teaching responsibilities, Fatima serves as the admissions and Registration officer of the Department of Architecture at Kaduna Polytechnic. She is also, a member of the Management Committee on Junior Staff Appointments and Promotions (MCJSA&PC) and the College of Environmental Studies conference committee (CES conference), among other roles. Her research interests primarily

revolve around Anti-Terrorism Crime Prevention and Security Design.

3

Hamza Ahmed Mora

He is a bilingual Architect who is fluent in both English and French languages. He graduated with an MSc in Architecture from the National School of Architecture, Rabat, Kingdom of Morocco. Musa is passionate about impacting architectural knowledge and has been lecturing at Kaduna Polytechnic for close to a decade. He is a member of the Association of Architectural Educators in Nigeria (AARCHES) and has a Provisional Membership with the Nigeria Institute of Architects (NIA).